

Sylow's Theorems

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Let G be a group of order $|G| = p^n m$ with p prime and m prime to p . A p -Sylow subgroup of G is, by definition, a subgroup of G of order p^n . (For any set S we write $|S|$ for the cardinality of S .)

Theorem 1. *If G is as above, then G has a Sylow p -subgroup.*

Theorem 2. *Let G be as above, let S be a Sylow p -subgroup, and let P be a p -subgroup of G . Then there is a g in G such that $gPg^{-1} \subset S$. In particular, Sylow p -subgroups are conjugate.*

Theorem 3. *Let G be as above, and let s be the number of Sylow p -subgroups of G . Then*

- (a) s divides m ,
- (b) $s \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$.

Proof of Theorems 1 and 3(b). ² It suffices to prove Theorem 3(b). Let G act on the set X of cardinality p^n subsets of G by $(g, A) \mapsto gA$, and, for $A \in X$ write X_A for the G -orbit of A . Let $\mathcal{S} \subset X$ be the set of Sylow p -subgroups of G . We claim

- (c) $S, T \in \mathcal{S}$ and $S \neq T$ imply $X_S \neq X_T$,
- (d) $S \in \mathcal{S}$ implies $|X_S| = m$,
- (e) $A \in X$ and $X_A \cap \mathcal{S} = \emptyset$ imply that p divides $|X_A|$.

Proof that (c), (d) and (e) imply Theorem 3(b): We have $|X| \equiv sm \pmod{p}$. In particular $s \pmod{p}$ depends only on the order of G . Since $\mathbb{Z}/|G|\mathbb{Z}$ is easily seen to have exactly one Sylow p -subgroup, we get $s \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, that is, Theorem 3(b), and, *a fortiori*, Theorem 1.

Proof of (c) and (d): This follows immediately from the fact that, for $S \in \mathcal{S}$, we have $X_S = \{gS \mid g \in G\} = G/S$.

Proof of (e): Set $B := a^{-1}A \in X_A$ with $a \in A$. The stabilizer H of B acting freely on B , we have $|H| = p^k$ with $0 \leq k \leq n$, hence $|X_A| = |G|/|H| = p^{n-k}m$, and it suffices to show $k \neq n$. Since $H \subset B$, the equality $k = n$ would imply $B = H \in X_A \cap \mathcal{S}$. \square

Proof of Theorem 2. Let S be a Sylow p -subgroup of G and P a p -subgroup of G . Set $X := G/S$ and note that $|X| = m$. The cardinality of any P orbit on X is of the form p^k with $0 \leq k \leq n$. It follows from Theorem 3(b) that P has at least one fixed point on X . This means that there is a g in G such that $PgS = gS$, that is $(g^{-1}Pg)S = S$, that is $g^{-1}Pg \subset S$. This proves the theorem. \square

Proof of Theorem 3(a). Let G act by conjugacy on the set \mathcal{S} of all Sylow p -subgroups of G . This action is transitive by Theorem 2. Let S be in \mathcal{S} . Since the stabilizer N of S (which is its normalizer) contains S , we see that $|S|$ divides $|N|$, hence $s = |G/N|$ divides $|G/S| = m$. \square

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²The proof below is taken from the text *Groupes finis* by Jean-Pierre Serre <https://arxiv.org/abs/math/0503154>.